

1 **Unbiased discovery of genes required for pluripotency: Lingo1.**

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6 Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency
7 as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the
8 multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and
9 embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We
10 describe identification of Lingo1 as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in the human
11 embryonic stem cell.

12 Citations

13 1. Mi, S., Miller, R.H., Lee, X., Scott, M.L., Shulag-Morskaya, S., Shao, Z., Chang, J., Thill, G.,
14 Levesque, M., Zhang, M. and Hession, C., 2005. LINGO-1 negatively regulates myelination by
15 oligodendrocytes. Nature neuroscience, 8(6), pp.745-751.